

Code as the expression of its own vitalism.

Luis Alfonso Tamagnini

Universidad Nacional de Rosario
bosca.music@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In her book My Mother Was a Computer: Digital Subjects and Literary Texts, literary theorist and critic Katherine Hayles posits that; as computers are increasingly understood, and modeled after “expressive mediums” like writing, they begin to acquire the familiar and potent capability of writing not merely to express thought but actively to constitute it.

The code of the future will become more like the writing of the past – or rather, in the future there will be an as-yet-concealed hybrid of code and writing.[1]

It is on this path on which I write this self essay about how I wrote and how I write computer music code. In it, I wonder about how formal language permeates the concepts of score, musical instrument, composition and performance among others. This structures becomes not only an expression of an abstract process or thought, but also an expression of itself, or of its own “vitalism”.

Furthermore, I allow myself to explore the live coding technique as a way to interact with this such a complex entities.

tags: computational creativity, music performance, interactive music systems, live coding, simulation, software studies, media theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the mid-50s of the XX century, when computers and computer languages were just beginning their fantastic development, a group of creators and artists produced a series of works that are now called “concrete poetry”. In these works, physical and formal aspects of language such as phonetics, typography and spatial arrange, punctuation, etc., along with other principles of formal languages such as generativity and algorithms, are fused and interspersed with the pure literary expression built over centuries of history of oral and written human communication.

It was within this extensive and eclectic ecosystem of writers, graphic artists, and audiovisual performers in witch I started to imagine how can formal languages such us computer programs can deal with the so called artistic expression. I wrote a little paper about the musical formal arrangement and aural implications in the work of Argentinian writer Oliverio Gironde in 2004 [2]. A direct path to code was almost obvious and I was soon programming my own algorithmic music.

This paper is an introduction to a further development in witch I will try to discuss some of the key concepts that I

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have been developing since that, both from an empirical point of view and with the support of contemporary knowledge on digital media and philosophy of technology.

2. THE SCORE

Perhaps the first and most obvious comparison between a piece of code and a musical object can be seen in the score. Musical scores are composed of a system of symbols and rules, and by this means can contain the representation of the temporal display of an abstract sound pattern.

Following this approach, the musical canon and most precisely, the enigmatic canon represents for me a beautiful example for such a cryptic formal system, intended to be also a piece of music.

I carry on with an old school fascination with enigmatic canons, so, in 2013 I started to code snippets of infinite, generative sonic structures with Supercollider. I was immediately engaged by the way in which a small amount of code or symbols can contain potentially endless music, loaded also with its own meaning.

I started working and exploring the boundaries of the pattern library in SC, but after that, I focused on Demand Ugens and the JITLib library, mostly because of the need to manage a shared set of raw data between multiple patterns, or simply to generate or transform that data in real time.

```
1 p.clock.tempo_(1.4);
2 x={exprand(1,111)}!3;
3 y={exprand(31,330)}!4;
4 ~track_1.rebuild;
5 r=1.0!7;
6 ~track_1.quant=1;
7 ~track_1={
8   var e,t,f,m,i;
9   e=Env.perc;
10  t=TDuty.ar(Dseq(r/~tempo.kr,inf),0);
11  f=Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq([60],inf));
12  i=Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq(x,inf));
13  m=Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq(y,inf));
14  MoogVCF.ar(SinOsc.ar([f,f+1]+SinOsc.ar(m,
15  0,i))*e.ar(0,t,Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq(r*0.5,inf)),1094)*0.5);
16 ~track_1.play;
```

Figure 1. A ~track_1 NodeProxy holding a function to generate a musical pattern from a set of predefined arrays of data.

Enigmatic canons are often based on mathematical relationships between voices, such as proportional tempos or intervallic transformations, so I coded a dictionary of custom functions to serve this purpose.

```

1 x={exprand(1,111)}!3;
2 y={exprand(31,330)}!4;
3 r=1.0!7;
4 r=f.at(\golden).value(r);
5 r=f.at(\redux).value(r);
6 y=f.at(\redux).value(y);
7 r=r.scramble;
8 ~track_1.rebuild;

```

Figure 2. Successive calls to different functions that generate or modify data on the fly.

```

1 f.add(\golden -> {|a| var p=a*(5.sqrt-1/2);p++(a-p)});

```

Figure 3. A dictionary hold custom functions to operate over arrayed sets. In this case the function split values on array generating two different new values related with the golden ratio.

These codes are, as scores, a blueprint for performers, providing all the necessary information to play the music as intended by the composer, but they are not for human performers, instead the performer it is a computer.

In Renaissance, enigmatic canons helped push the boundaries of musical composition, exploring new possibilities for structure and expression. Today, I find the same paradigm by writing this code snippets, exploring them as containers for its own (maybe) infinite sonic enigma.

3. THE INSTRUMENT

Another huge and interesting path can be traced through the concepts of machine, musical instrument and code (or algorithm). This is, by sheer logic, an enormous amount of work that can easily reflect the very history of the human being. In order to focus on some very personal points of interest, I choose the Simondonian concept of “technical object” [3] to order my thinking and serve as a conceptual basis.

My fascination with music and machines grew at the same moment and in the same act, watching my 80's stars make incredible futuristic sounds flow from their black boxes with fluorescent buttons called synthesizers. This influenced my future interest in two very specific areas, music and technology, and shortly after the brain explosion of delving into Franco-Flemish polyphony and ultimately on Bach's "logical counterpoint", in the early days of the web, I discovered a piece of software called (maybe) aeTM3_3!; for me, simply “Autechre generative sequencer”.

I think I found this Max patch in 2004 or 2005, and despite conjectures about its origin or authors, I spent hours

listening to its continuing evolving flow of synthetic sounds and melodies.

I started to imagine the future of the musical objects as, just pieces of data and logical information packaged on very little binary files, containing an endless amount of music, capable of be interpreted by any computer on the world and beyond and easily shared over digital nets.

Back to Simondon, for him, a technical object is not just a tool or machine; it is a system that undergoes development and adaptation over time. It has a "life" of its own, shaped by its internal logic and its interactions with its environment.

aeTM3_3 it is essentially a Max/MSP patch. In such a graphic programming environment, a button or a number box can be something fully automated or something over which someone can apply a delivered action to trigger some sudden formal disruption, or some subtle timbral modulation.

Moreover, a very interest issue around this process of tweaking over the algorithm behavior is that the musical experiences become a two way conversational process between the machine intrinsic logic and the human ear or musical hearing.

This hybridization between machine and musical instrument or interface becomes a main subject of research in my work.

```

1 ~track_1={
2   var e,t,f,m,i;
3   e=Env.perc;t=TDuty.ar(Dseq(r/~tempo.kr,inf),0);
4   f=Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq([60],inf));
5   i=Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq(x,inf));
6   m=Demand.ar(t,0,Dseq(y,inf));
7   MoogVCF.ar(SinOsc.ar(~cc_3*[f,f+1]+SinOsc.ar(m
0,i))*e.ar(0,t,Demand.ar(t,
0,Dseq(r*~cc_2,inf))),~cc_0*1094+20,~cc_1)*0.5);
8 ~track_1.play;

```

Figure 4. In this example we can see how can “inject” control NodeProxys into ~ track_1 to modify and add live control over some inner parameters.

4. COMPOSITION

To address this question I will mention the work of Fredrik Olofsson. His “setwitz” aroused my curiosity to investigate the potential hidden in this short code snippets, and, as he says, to get "inside the structure of a particular piece of code". A particular piece of code that is, like an enigmatic canon, the container for a possible endless arrange of sounds, carry on with its own meaning.

He refers to these musical objects as "miniature compositions" [4] and describes the compositional process as a "mind-machine feedback loop". I mentioned this concept earlier when I talked about the "two way conversational process" involved in tweak the algorithm while it is running, and I will address it again later when I will talk about performance and live coding.

Olofsson argues that, "my mind and my computer's CPU are like coprocessors - or like two halves of a brain - working in tandem on the same problem. One is dealing with the given problem in theory and the other in practice".

The same algorithms are running both on the computer and in my mind. They are working in parallel but in completely different ways. Compared to the CPU, my brain funnels out and deals more with predictive evaluation - processes linked to how the code could or might sound. It takes into account what just has happened and future possibilities. The CPU, on the other hand (...) does not do any of that. It just autonomously executes the work here and now 'unaware' of what it is doing. It is concrete and plays its part in the larger system, the mind-machine feedback loop (...).

5. PERFORMANCE

At this point, the compositional process becomes deeply intertwined with performance. Moreover, similarities with other musical systems such as modular synthesizers can be considered. From this idea I started to think about a (so called by me) hybrid system for my performance setup.

In this hybrid system, two different subsystems that share many common properties work together by exchanging information, resulting in a single common output.

I started to be fascinated with the idea of write codes that can trigger and/or generate signals to be routed to a modular synthesis system. While this concept is perhaps not new, the motivation behind this search is to adopt the idea of a "live coded" modular synthesizer. This is, controlling analog signals not just by tweaking knobs and buttons, but also by writing and modifying codes on performance.

Figure 5. This picture illustrates how this setup is seen from the hardware side. This setup is for the live performances with my project `\unexCoder`²

```
1 // >> two channels gate/cv
2 ~track_6={
3     var trig =Impulse.ar(1);
4     [trig,DC.ar(0.05)]*0.8
5 }
```

Figure 6. A very simple NodeProxy generating a two channels signal to control both cv and gate on an analog synthesizer.

```
1 ~sig.play(8)
2 ~sig={DC.ar(0.1)}
3
4 // 1v/oct - exp FM
5 ~sig={DC.ar(-1*0.0969)}
6
7 // lin FM
8 ~sig={DC.ar(0.1)}
9 ~sig={LinExp.ar(DC.ar(-1))}
10 ~sig={Saw.ar(1,0.1)}
11 ~sig.clear;
```

Figure 7. A live code session flow that shows how a single NodeProxy is used to carry on different kinds of frequency modulation on the analog instrument.

6. LIVE CODING

Live coding, or conversational programming, is generally described as, the act of write or modify the source code for a program while it is running. This is a very contemporary practice carried on by artists around the world making music, visuals, and other performance arts. This practice can be achieved in Supercollider with a couple of different techniques, however, mastering live-coding in this language is a challenging task. As I mentioned earlier, I prefer to use the JITLib library and the ProxySpace paradigm. By this mean, I can work with a number of nodes to live code on, and a set of environment variables to share data between these nodes, and to hold other globally access information such as Midi or OSC connections, clocks, etc. I also use environment variables as dictionaries to hold audio files and custom functions to generate or modify arranges of data.

In this particular approach, code, as a system of symbols and rules, and live-coding as a practical solution are working as the glue that serves to give formal structure to the complex musical ecosystem shared by score, composition, instrument and performance.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The intellectual effort of ordering the ideas and tools related to an artist's work is a task that we do not always entrust to ourselves. However, it is an invaluable exercise, especially for those of us who work in a closed link with today's technological tools. In relation to my work, it has helped me to build a retrospective, and to understand how the techniques I use today, especially music computing and live coding, relate to my musical history.

Acknowledgments

To my lovely noiser, Mica.

8. REFERENCES

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